

Prof. HKT Raza (1956-2019)

Prof. Dr Haroon Khizir Taqi Raza, an internationally renowned Orthopaedic surgeon is not with us physically due to his sudden demise on 14th March, 2019 but he will always be remembered as a dynamic extraordinary academic leader in the Orthopaedic world nationally and internationally. After his under graduation (1978) and post-graduation (1982), he worked as a faculty in the Department of Orthopaedics at GRMC Medical College, Gwalior and at NSCB Medical College, Jabalpur. He headed the Department of Orthopaedics, NSCB Medical College for almost more than 20 years. In the department, he was always involved in undergraduate and postgraduate teaching. With his special interest in spinal surgery, he was the man behind the establishment of Regional Spinal Injury Center at Jabalpur and with his efforts more than 100 posts were created in that center. He was involved in the development of sub-specialties in the department. He taught many not only the academics but the high values of life like full dedication to work, sincerity and organizational skill. He was the founder Dean of Chindwara Institute of Medical Science. He took the Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh to such a height that Jabalpur became the synonymous with name of Dr Taqi Raza among the orthopaedic fraternity worldwide. His original research work on trabecular pattern in the femoral head, designing cobrahood plate for subtrochanteric fracture, hockey stick plate for supracondylar femur and muscle pedicle graft for chronic osteomyelitis was well appreciated in the

scientific meetings all over. He was the editor of Journal of Orthopaedics, MP Chapter for 6 years. With his efforts, for the first time national conference of Indian Orthopaedic association (IOACON) in 1998 was held in the Jabalpur which made the history in the excellence of hospitality in spite of meager infrastructure to cater more than 5000 persons at that time. It was due his public goodwill and face-value that for the first time public supported wholeheartedly to make national conference a grand success and Jabalpur stood the first for that. Jabalpur is still remembered for the hospitality, academics and interaction between members of Indian Orthopaedic Association for IOACON 1998. After grand success of conference, he contested and became the Honorary Secretary of IOA and remained for two terms. During his tenure, emphasis on postgraduate teaching, affiliation of state chapters to IOA and publication of newsletter was given. During this period, he was also the man behind the formation of the blue book of Indian Orthopaedic Association. Further he became the youngest President of IOA in 2006 and he gave the theme of his presidency "Focus on Golden Hour" for trauma victims and organized the awareness programs nationwide with free distribution of CD on first Aid. He started IOA-AOA exchange fellowship with Australian Orthopaedic Association and IOS-UK with British Orthopaedic Association to facilitate international exposure for the members of Indian Orthopaedic Association. He started the social Orthopaedic society of

India and he started Teachers training program first time. He had setup 100 bedded temporary hospital to help the earthquake victim of Bhuj Gujarat and Indian Orthopaedic association send him to Nepal during Earthquake in Kathmandu. He had made more than 170 publications and scientific deliberations to his credit and got several fellowships and awards including the prestigious A. A. Mehta Gold medal, J & J fellowship and the most prestigious award of IOA – Dr. B. N. Sinha award. He had organized the Asia Pacific Orthopaedic Association (APOA) congress 2012 at New Delhi and also became the First Indian President of APOA, taking his glory to the international level. On the eve of Doctors day,

Government of Madhya Pradesh honored him with appreciation letter remembering his works towards the upliftment of medical Education.

Sudden demise of Prof Raza is an irreparable loss, which have filled the hearts of not only the Orpaedians worldwide but for the whole of the society with deep sorrow and sadness. He shall be always remembered in our hearts.

Dr Krishna K Pandey

Associate Professor,
Department of Orthopaedics, NSCB Medical
College, Jabalpur (M.P.), India

Address of correspondence:

Dr Krishna Kumar Pandey, Associate Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Traumatology and Rehabilitation, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose Medical College, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India. Email - drpandeykk@yahoo.com-

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